

From Awareness to Action: Gender-Sensitive Behaviour Gap Among Gen Z in Indian Higher Education

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ABSTRACT: In Indian higher education, conversations about gender equality and inclusivity are becoming more common, especially among Generation Z students who are perceived to be more aware because of digital media. Grounded in the theory of planned behaviour and gender socialisation, it attempts to understand the relationship between gender-sensitive behaviour and attitude towards gender equality. Using a mixed-methods approach, it explores how various factors, such as age, gender, and income, influence gender-sensitive behaviour patterns among Generation Z in selected higher educational institutions. It aims to explore how institutional and digital spaces shape gender-sensitive behaviours.

Quantitative results from 125 participants indicate moderate-to-high theoretical gender sensitivity, with female participants and those under 18 demonstrating higher sensitivity levels. However, qualitative findings from focus group discussions reveal a gap in the awareness paradox, where high theoretical empathy coexists with deeply entrenched biases, such as the delegitimisation of female technical competence in STEM, restrictive campus curfews, and identifying gender issues as women's issues. The paper argues that to address the gap between awareness and action, there is a need to shift from rights-based awareness to gender-transformative interventions that focus on experiential learning, accountability and active involvement in shaping gender-sensitive behaviour in higher educational spaces that dismantle the structural patriarchal barriers.

KEYWORDS: Gender sensitivity, Gender equality, Youth, Higher Education, Generation Z

I. INTRODUCTION

Gender equality is widely acknowledged as an essential element of sustainable development and is explicitly incorporated within the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), notably Goal 5. The discussion about gender equality and inclusivity has become very common in Indian institutional spaces. In recent years, colleges and universities have been seen as important places for young people to learn to be more sensitive to gender issues, as they shape values, social norms, and future leaders. In this context, Generation Z is frequently depicted as socially conscious, progressive, and as advocates for gender equity, primarily due to enhanced access to education, digital media, and global discussions on rights and inclusion.

According to the All India Survey of Higher Education (AISHE), around 4.33 crores of students were enrolled in Indian higher education in 2021-22. Higher education is important in developing the mindset of today's youth. Although it is assumed that the youths are more aware of gender issues in the contemporary world, it is still not clear how gender sensitivity gets translated into everyday behaviour. A significant portion of the current literature regarding gender and youth has concentrated on measuring attitudes and perceptions or examining structural inequalities. Consequently, there is a lack of empirical insight into whether self-reported gender sensitivity among youth signifies substantive behavioural change or merely indicates conformity to socially desirable values.

This study examines the correlation between gender sensitivity and behavioural practices among Generation Z students in Indian higher education, thereby addressing an existing gap. Employing a mixed-methods framework, the study integrates quantitative assessments of gender sensitivity with qualitative insights derived from focused group discussions to investigate the expression, negotiation, and occasional contradiction of these attitudes in everyday lives.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Understanding Gender Sensitivity

In simple words, recognising and addressing the gendered differences, roles and inequalities can be comprehended as gender sensitivity. It involves both the knowledge and intent to practice inclusivity in everyday interaction and actions.

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Gender sensitivity is situated in the middle of the spectrum from gender negative to gender transformative change (Christodoulou, 2005; Zobnina, 2009). Thus, gender sensitivity is a mental construct that helps people question the existing gender-biased societal norms, roles and the social system and endorse equal participation and fair distribution of benefits (UNDP, 2001).

Existing literature shows that gender-sensitive attitudes help to reduce gender-based discrimination and promote social solidarity. Different agents of socialisation, such as family and peer socialisation, formal education, and media impact, may influence the development of a gender-sensitive mindset among youth (Kalra et al., 2021; Aulia et al., 2024).

Review of literature suggests that the youth's attitude and awareness towards gender sensitivity is not widely practised in society (Casas et al., 2024). Gender awareness does not happen mechanically (Dorji, 2020). Studies highlight the importance of gender sensitivity training in increasing the awareness and changing one's attitude towards gender issues (Casas et al., 2024). However, most of the literature on gender sensitivity is situated within the context of school students (Kalra et al., 2021; Aulia et al., 2024; Jha et al., 2020).

B. Gender Sensitivity in the context of Generation Z

As youth are the future of the country, they are significant in restructuring the gendered norms with the help of education and social media activism. People born between 1997 and 2012 are part of Generation Z. They are the first true digital natives because they grew up with the internet and social media. Some studies show in what way youth question the patriarchal structure, endorse workplace equity and promote participatory governance. However, it also highlights the challenges in the form of digital divide and intersectional inequalities (Prajapati, 2024).

Similarly, the UDAYA longitudinal study in Bihar and Uttar Pradesh found that adolescents generally became more egalitarian over time, with girls showing stronger shifts toward equity than boys. Factors such as family communication, peer networks, and schooling play a decisive role in shaping these attitudes. Existing literature shows that the older boys may have regressive behaviour. They may also reinforce gender inequality (Patel, Santhya, & Haberland, 2021). As a result, youth gender sensitivity is not constant; it is contingent upon context and may be impacted by a variety of social factors.

C. Gender Sensitivity and Higher Education

In order to advance gender equality and guarantee equal opportunity and development, education is an essential institution (Abraha, Dagnew & Seifu, 2019). Gender sensitivity is crucial in education because it fosters equality, reduces gender-based discrimination, boosts self-esteem, and cultivates inclusivity and respect (Nair, 2024). Review of literature suggests that although the enrolment rates are higher in colleges, the completion rates of higher education are significantly lower. For instance, a study shows that only 51% young male students complete their education by 26 years, whereas only 35% the female students can complete their education because of various challenges, such as females have to start working at an early stage, either at home or outside, from a younger age, therefore, they struggle more to complete their education. Moreover, the problem of early marriage, patriarchal gender roles, caste, poverty etc. further complicate their situation. Thus, gender sensitivity is not adequately reflected in the enrolment rates, we need to identify the factors that hinder completion of education, empowerment and sustainability (Singh, Mukherjee, & Kumar, 2023).

D. Gender Equality and Higher Education

Studies on gender equality in higher education highlight that although the enrolment rates of women have increased, the problem persists because of gender stereotypes, not adequate inclusion in STEM fields and leadership opportunities. Studies incorporating gender awareness into education is crucial if we hope to practice equality and empowerment in the future (Singh, 2025).

Although there is extensive literature related to gender sensitivity among adolescents, there is a limited number of studies that address the gender sensitive behaviour and perception of the youth, particularly the Gen Z. And, there are also a limited number of studies that link gender sensitivity and gender equality in the context of youth of the 21st century which has increasingly digitalised. The integration of gender-equitable activities by young people has not been thoroughly examined in the literature. This disparity highlights the necessity of a mixed-method approach that can simultaneously capture statistical trends and qualitative insights into how youth negotiate gender and sustainable principles of social justice and gender equity.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study has the following objectives:

- A. The study explores the relationship between gender-sensitive behaviour patterns and attitudes towards gender equality;
- B. To explore the gender sensitivity patterns across the variables such as income, gender and age of the Gen Z students;
- C. To explore how institutional and digital spaces influence gender-sensitive behaviour and gender equality

IV. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theory of planned behaviour and gender socialisation theory are used in this study to understand the connection between youth behavioural practices and gender sensitivity. According to the theory of planned behaviour, three main factors, such as personal attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control, have an impact on behaviour. Subjective norms capture the impact

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of societal expectations, attitudes represent personal ideas about a behaviour, and perceived behavioural control is a person's assessment of their capacity to carry out the behaviour. This concept emphasises that as actions are frequently influenced by social and contextual restrictions, positive attitudes by themselves are insufficient to guarantee commensurate behavioural consequences (Ajzen, 1991).

In parallel, gender socialisation theory describes how socialisation processes cause people to internalise gender norms and roles. People are exposed to culturally defined expectations about gender-appropriate behaviour from an early age, and these expectations eventually become profoundly ingrained. These internalized standards frequently continue to influence behaviour in subtle and occasionally unconscious ways, even in the face of shifting views or heightened awareness (Eagly, 1987; Ridgeway, 2011).

When combined, these frameworks offer a conceptual foundation for comprehending gender sensitivity as an important term that includes both behavioural and attitudinal elements. Gender Socialization Theory emphasizes the long-lasting effects of internalized standards, whereas the Theory of Planned Behavior stresses the significance of perceived limitations and external social influences. A more thorough analysis of how gender sensitivity is articulated and performed in social contexts is made possible by this combined perspective.

V. MATERIALS AND METHODS

We used a mixed-method approach in the design of this study to explore the relationship between gender sensitivity and behavioral practices among Gen Z students in higher education. Thus, the study uses survey and focused group discussion as a method of data collection. By examining the data and delving into actual experiences, this mixed-methods approach enabled us to identify trends and comprehend the narratives that underlie them. The findings are triangulated by using various sources.

Between November 2025 and January 2026, the study was carried out in particular regions of India's National Capital Region (NCR) and Uttarakhand. Participants were drawn from STEM-focused colleges and universities. The study included young people who were present and involved during the data collection days and were between the ages of 14 and 25. People who weren't there on that particular day didn't take part.

The Gender-Equitable Men (GEM) Scale and the International Men and Gender Equality Survey (IMAGES) are two well-known tools that we used to construct a structured questionnaire to measure gender sensitivity among the youth. The questionnaire had two sections: one for basic demographic information and another for statements about gender sensitivity in various domains, such as gender rights, policies, attitudes about roles and equality, behaviour in social or academic settings, digital citizenship, empathy, bias, and willingness to change. Students answered on a five-point scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree". The semi-structured questionnaire was distributed in the classroom setting.

We held focus groups to gain a deeper understanding of students' perspectives on gender sensitivity and how it relates to social sustainability. Using a semi-structured guide, we conducted eight focus-group discussions with a diverse group of fifty Gen Z students. Personal experiences with gender sensitivity, opinions on equality and inclusion, the function of education, and digital media were all discussed.

To identify general patterns in gender sensitivity, we imported all of the survey data into statistical software and primarily examined descriptive statistics. Additionally, we planned more thorough investigations, such as determining a Gender Sensitivity Index (GSI) and examining connections between important factors. Only after we had completed all of the calculations were the results reported. Every word from the group conversations was transcribed, and the data was thematically analysed. This required revisiting raw data multiple times, classifying answers, and organising related concepts into more comprehensive themes. This made it easier for us to identify trends and extract information about young sustainability and gender sensitivity. We combined the results from the focus groups and the survey at the conclusion. To provide a more complete picture of how gender sensitivity influences young people's perspectives on sustainability, we compared the data with what we heard in conversations.

A. Data analysis

In order to analyse the survey data, we reverse-coded negatively phrased items so that all scores ranged from 1 to 5, with higher scores indicating more favourable opinions. After calculating the overall domain scores by adding the item scores within each domain, we divided the individuals into three groups: high (scores of 4–5), moderate (3), and low (1–2). We compared these groups according to age, gender, and income, and we displayed the findings as percentages and index values (M).

We read the transcripts multiple times to familiarize ourselves with the topic before methodically coding the responses for the qualitative data. Similar codes were categorized and then arranged into more general topics and domains. Through this method, we were able to identify recurrent trends and develop meaningful themes to address how gender sensitivity and gender equality are shaped in the everyday lives of Generation Z.

B. Ethical considerations

Approval for the study was obtained from the IQAC of the Inderprastha Engineering College, Ghaziabad. We have taken prior permission from the participating institutional authorities. Informed verbal consent was taken from all participants. The participants were given an orientation that their participation was voluntary. We have ensured the privacy, confidentiality and anonymity of

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participants and institutions.

VI. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

A. Socio-Demographic Profile

In the study, almost half (47.2%) belonged to the middle-income group, while 35.2% were categorised as high-income and 20.0% as low-income, of the total 125 participants. The gender distribution was mostly balanced, with almost equal distribution of 49.6% male and 50.4% female participants. In terms of age, most participants (72.0%) were more than 18 years, whereas 28.0% were younger than 18 years, as illustrated in Table I.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Participants (N= 125)

Demographic Indicators	Sub-Categories	Percentage of Study Participants
Income	Low-income (below 10000)	20%
	Middle-income (above ₹10,000, below ₹50,000)	47.2%
	High-income (above ₹50,000)	35.2%
Gender	Male	49.6 %
	Female	50.4 %
Age Group	Below 18 (14 -17 years)	28.0 %
	Above 18	72.0%

B. Quantitative Findings: Gender-Sensitive Behaviour Patterns Across Demographic Variables

To understand Generation Z's mindset and attitude towards gender equality, a gender-sensitivity index (GSI) was analysed across three socio-demographic dimensions, such as age, gender, and income, as illustrated in Table 2 and corresponding figures. By and large, the data indicate a moderate-to-high level of gender sensitivity across all cohorts, with GSI scores ranging from 3.70 to 4.40 on a 5-point scale.

Table 2: Distribution of Gender Sensitivity Index score by Demographic Indicators

Demographic indicators	Sub-categories	Total GSI
1. Income	Low-income (below Rs. 10,000)	3.70
	Middle income (above Rs. 10,000, below 50,000)	3.84
	High-income (above Rs 50,000)	3.89
2. Gender	Male	3.74
	Female	4.03
4. Age group	below 18	3.99
	above 18	3.80

a) Age-Based Variations

As illustrated in Figure I, participants under the age of 18 showed a higher overall GSI (M = 3.99) in contrast to those aged 18 and above (M=3.80). The most significant difference occurred in the sub-categories of *attitudes* (4.35 vs. 4.03) and *willingness for intervention* (4.17 vs. 3.83). Data shows that age groups showed their lowest performance in identifying *Implicit Bias*, with the scores of 3.48 and 3.72, respectively.

Figure 1: Gender Sensitivity by Age

b) Gender-Based Disparities

The data highlights significant variations in terms of gender. Female participants showed a GSI of 4.03, with male participants recording the lowest score in this category (GSI of 3.74) as illustrated in Table 2. Analysis of the data by gender highlights a uniform ‘gender-sensitivity gap’, as female participants outperform male participants, across all seven indicators (Figure 3). The most significant disparity was highlighted in attitudes towards gender roles, where females scored 4.26 compared to 3.45 for males, with a difference of 0.81 points. Females also showed higher levels of empathy (4.28) and behaviour (4.20) in social and academic setting.

Figure 2: Gender Sensitivity by Gender

c) Economic Status and Sensitivity

The data shows a positive linear trend between household income and gender sensitivity. The study participants from the high - income category showed the highest GSI of 3.89. This was followed by the middle-income category, with a GSI of 3.84, and the low-income category, with a GSI of 3.70, as illustrated in Table 2.

Figure 4 shows a positive linear trend between income and digital citizenship, with scores rising from 3.94 in the low-income category to 4.24 in the high-income category. On the contrary, awareness of rights and policies was highest among the low- income group (3.78) and lowest in the high-income group (3.59). It is pertinent to mention that, irrespective of these variations, the bias category remained the lowest-scoring parameter across all income brackets (M is approximately 3.50).

Figure 3: Gender Sensitivity by Income Level Qualitative Findings: The Lived Reality

d) Normalisation of the gender issue as a women’s issue

One of the common themes that was highlighted from the FGDs with the male participants was that they could not relate to the questions asked during the FGDs such as what do they understand by gender, gender sensitivity. Some of them shared, “We think you should discuss this with the female colleagues, gender or gender issues are not relevant to us. I’m proud of being a boy.” The majority of the FGDs highlight how the patriarchal biases and stereotypical gender norms are reflected in the everyday discussions and behaviour. Thus, they were finding it difficult to acknowledge any gender issues or concerns.

e) Normalisation of Bias in STEM Pedagogy

The narratives highlight a pedagogical invisibility of female technical competence in higher educational institutions. Female students in STEM programs described an environment in which both peers and faculty routinely delegitimise their intellectual labour. In FGDs, groups of female participants shared, “When we were given a group project presentation, female teachers preferred to have discussions about the technical parts, like coding, with the male students. It’s frustrating, we put 100% effort, but sometimes we feel our efforts are not recognised. It is assumed we have less understanding” This narrative suggests that even though the women may hold positions of authority, they may perpetuate the patriarchal bias that technical expertise is a male attribute. Another student added, “Our male friends said that since we are girls, we have pretty privilege.” This shows how academic and career success are linked with beauty, which mocks their professional worth.

f) The Safety-Agency Compromise

Institutional responses to safety concerns for female students were found to manifest as restrictions on female autonomy. A protectionist framework that is characterized by 7:00 PM curfews or in-time, applies to female students only. In one of the FGDs, female students stated, “The problem is that we don’t go out after 7 pm... They say it is for our safety.” Although framed as protective, these measures prevent female students from learning the informal curriculum. Thus, restricting their involvement in sports, collaborations and networking post 7 pm, which are crucial for holistic development. By equating safety with surveillance, institutions reinforce the notion that public space belongs to men and private space belongs to women.

g) Digital Duality and the Culture of Silence

Although social media contributes to high digital GSI parameters, it could also facilitate meme culture and sexism. Students reported being judged online for their clothing or social choices, which indicates a performative sensitivity, where youth can articulate rights in a survey but consume content that reinforces binaries. Moreover, a lack of trust in grievance mechanisms was evident. Regarding reporting harassment, students highlighted the teacher’s discouraging response, as discussed in the FGDs: “She said ...he is a boy, what if he does something when you are outside... be more careful.” While some narratives highlight that teachers tried to resolve the issue, the narrative suggests a victim-blaming tendency, as the burden of safety lies on the victim. Thus, it can be inferred that formal policies, such as the Internal Complaint Committee (ICC), are disguised as mere procedures, which exist on paper.

VII. DISCUSSION: Addressing the disparity between gender sensitive behaviour and attitude among the Gen Z

One of the contributions of this study is the identification of the awareness paradox of sensitivity among Gen Z. Although the quantitative data suggest that youth possess a high degree of theoretical empathy, the qualitative evidence indicates that this sensitivity is often fragile. It mostly works in the abstract but fails to function in everyday practices and actions, for instance, within the social pressures of the classroom. This deviation is parallel with the value-action gap (Kollmuss & Agyeman, 2002), which

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suggests that internal knowledge does not inevitably translate into behavioural change; deeply ingrained structural and individual barriers are the source of these behaviours. Despite the introduction of the rhetoric of equality through educational initiatives in India, it seems that the underlying patriarchal structure that controls the lived experience is still widespread in reality, which prevents the path towards gender equality.

A. Linking Theory with Findings

The disparity between gender-sensitive behavioural practices and self-reported gender sensitivity can be explained by using the Theory of Planned Behaviour. Although participants show positive sentiment towards gender sensitivity, their actions seem to be influenced by institutional challenges and prevalent social norms, such as peer expectations and gender biases. This means that situational constraints may reinforce pre-existing habits, and positive attitudes are not enough to bring behavioural change.

The qualitative results, which demonstrate the persistence of minor gender biases, are also in line with gender socialisation theory. Despite increased awareness, deeply rooted gender norms still shape attitudes and behaviour, particularly when it comes to acceptance of gendered restrictions and perceptions of competence. These findings imply that gender sensitivity may coexist with deeply ingrained, unalterable behavioural tendencies at the awareness level.

When taken as a whole, the findings provide credence to the idea that the relationship between awareness and conduct is influenced by both external social influences and internalised cultural standards. This highlights the need for approaches that go beyond merely altering attitudes to address the more significant institutional and social factors that impact behaviour.

B. Internalised Patriarchy against Gender Sensitivity

The discrepancy between strong female GSI ratings and the documented high pedagogical bias in STEM indicates that gender sensitivity is only seen as a formal necessity rather than a basic change in thinking. Especially, the observation that female faculty represents a basic change in thinking. Especially, the observation that female faculty also display such biases indicates that patriarchy is a pervasive ideology that is internalised across genders. This result supports the claims made by Moss-Racusin et al. (2012) that scientific teachers, regardless of their own gender, frequently unconsciously believe that male pupils are more capable. Parallely, Cech (2013) contends that the "technical" framing of STEM frequently serves as a cloak since it permits individuals to overlook social inequalities under the illusion of impartiality.

Our findings about the pedagogical invisibility and the disregard for women's academic accomplishments are consistent with Singh's (2025) observations. Gender stereotypes in STEM are still common, despite the fact that more women are enrolling in higher education. Singh discusses the potential for change brought about by more inclusive curricula. However, our research indicates that these changes seem incredibly superficial. Even female teachers internalize gender biases, making change difficult.

C. Questioning Gender Sensitivity: Restrictive Mobility as a Protective Approach

Framing restrictive mobility as a protective approach does not ensure gender sensitivity. Gender sensitivity can't be achieved by ensuring restrictive mobility in the name of protection but ensuring equal access and opportunities to people across genders. Nonetheless, we are unable to accomplish this goal when the women's movement is restricted for safety.

The findings are parallel to the study by Phadke, Khan, and Ranade (2011) noted that we end up restricting women's freedom and rights as citizens when we discuss their access to public space primarily in terms of safety or protection. If we exclude half of the population, we will not be able to achieve gender equality. We need to create a safe space that doesn't limit people's agency, regardless of gender identification.

D. Digital Literacy and Inclusivity

In the context of digital media, our data indicates a high GSI; nonetheless, sexism and the culture of memes were common practices. Similar to what Ging and Siapera (2018) noted, people can display their sensitivity on digital platforms, but those same venues also can make fun of important gender concerns.

According to Prajapati (2024), youth are actual change agents who use digital literacy to oppose patriarchy. The meme culture in relation to sexism and the performative nature of online sensitivity found in our study suggest that digital engagement has both positive and negative consequences. Thus, Gen Z require a critical digital literacy perspective to challenge these gendered norms.

E. Need for Intervention

The identified gap in the behaviour and action can be addressed with the help of interventions that emphasise experiential learning, accountability, and active involvement within the higher education spaces. There is also a need to create a safe institutional space where the faculty or the authorities don't reinforce the gender biased norms and behaviours. Thus, the study proposed an understanding of gender sensitivity among Generation Z that offers meaningful ways for translating awareness into meaningful actions. Moreover, there is also a need for intervention in digital spaces that shapes the mindset and the behaviour of the youth because today's Gen Z population are heavily driven by the digital media.

VIII. CONCLUSION

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The study attempts to understand how the idea of gender equality and gender sensitivity are perceived and practised among the Gen Z students in higher education. Contextualised in North India, the study highlights the gap between Gen Z students' self-reported gender sensitivity and the behaviour patterns in higher educational spaces. The study uses a mixed-method design to understand the relationship between attitude towards gender equality and gender sensitive behaviour among the Gen Z, it also attempts to understand how the gender sensitivity is influenced by variables such as age, gender and income. And, the role of higher educational institutions and digital media in shaping the gender sensitive behaviour among the Gen Z.

The triangulation of data shows a major gap in the findings as the qualitative findings show that gender sensitive views are not adequately reflected in the everyday interactions. However, the quantitative findings highlight that there is a moderate to high level of gender-sensitive attitude among Gen Z. Nonetheless, the findings also underscore that the gender sensitivity is relatively higher among females and the relatively younger youths.

It shows how theoretical knowledge of gender sensitivity coexists with social biases. The study helps us to uncover how the youth are aware of gender equality as reflected in high GSI scores mentioned in the paper, yet qualitative exploration reflects a gap in practice. The awareness is not yet translated into transformative everyday interactions and practices. The qualitative narratives, viz., the depiction of gender-biased classroom behaviour and protectionist curfews in campus life, gender issues as issues only related to women, reflect the need for a gender-sensitive perspective in society.

There is a persistent value-action gap within educational institutions as inferred from this paper. The society has raised a generation who are aware of gender sensitivity as an ideal behaviour, but are not been translated into actions. Thus, the society functions within a patriarchal structure and promotes control in the name of safety, and prefers to silence the victims. Therefore, we need to go beyond performative awareness to achieve gender equality. We need to move towards gender sensitive and transformative interventions. This can help us to challenge the structural barriers of society that lead to behavioural changes and attitudes of people. The study implies the need for an intervention that shapes the mindset of Gen Z to move towards gender equality. Thus, the study suggests that higher educational institutions must move beyond a culture of protection to a culture of empowerment to align with gender equality, SGD 5. This means reducing biases in pedagogy, ensuring free mobility, irrespective of gender. It also involves building a functional grievance mechanism that people can rely on. Thus, by reducing the gap between awareness and action, it can be ensured that the youth can become active agents of change in creating a sustainable society. Therefore, there is a need for intervention that transforms the youth mindset and achieves the larger sustainable goals of gender equality. Thus, the interventions should focus on experiential learning, accountability and active involvement in shaping gender sensitive behaviour in the higher educational spaces. Also, there is a need for gender sensitive digital interventions that can help in shaping the mindset. There is also a need to dismantle the patriarchal biases and gender stereotypes that are in the human resources involved in the institutional spaces; thus, the study proposes a need for a gender-transformative mindset and behaviour that addresses the gap between gender sensitivity and behaviour among Generation Z.

Although the study gives important insights regarding the behaviour and attitude gap among the Gen Z, the social desirability bias is one of the limitations as the students may give responses that are in line with gender equity discourses then with their actual lived behaviour. Future research may take a longitudinal approach to examine how gender sensitivity changes as young people go from school to the workforce. There is also a need for research that moves beyond the gender binary to explore how intersectional factors such as caste, disability, and diverse gender identities. Furthermore, with the rise of meme culture and its role in trivializing sexism, future work should evaluate the effectiveness of critical digital literacy programs in nurturing genuine instead of performative sensitivity. Finally, expanding this research to other geographic regions and exploring whether specific gender sensitive interventions can effectively reduce the gap between awareness and behaviour among youth will be an important and interesting area of study.

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